

RELIGION, HIV & STIGMA IN KENYA

A STUDY ON THE INFLUENCE OF RELIGION ON STIGMA FACED BY KEY POPULATIONS IN KENYA

BY

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Introduction & Methods

In Kenya, FBOs provide a large proportion of HIV services and the general population expresses high trust in FBOs. However, religion is also a powerful social force used to justify discrimination among key populations (KP). In such a context, it is important to identify FBOs that effectively offer HIV services to KP groups, explore how KP groups perceive FBOs and learn how religion can be a resource for KP members. This applied research initiative presents opportunities for improved practice in HIV prevention, treatment, and support.

We used a qualitative approach and collected data through key informant interviews and focus group discussions with FBOs, mature minors (MM), men who have sex with men (MSM), people who inject drugs (PWID) and female sex workers (FSW) in six counties in Kenya.

Table of Study Participants

KP	Type	# of events	# of participants
FBOs	KII	5	5
MM	FGD	4	42
MSM	FGD	4	42
	KII	5	5
PWID	FGD	4	30
	KII	4	4
FSW	FGD	6	61
	KII	1	1
Total		33	190

Key Findings

We found that KP members experienced stigma and discrimination at home, school, work, places of worship, and in health facilities. This happened across all KP groups interviewed, but specific experiences of stigma and discrimination varied. We learned that religion was at times a source for stigma and other times it alleviated stigma. For example, religion influenced stigma in many ways. Religion motivated FBOs to serve key population members and it made some key population members feel unwelcome at health facilities. Religion affirmed those who faced stigma but it also created self-stigma for others.

Recommendations

What you can do

- Show compassion and concern
- Pray and reflect on your attitudes so that you might demonstrate more love toward KP groups
- Learn about best practices and integrate them into your work
- Know about referral resources for different KP groups in your area
- Consider working with peer educators and advocates

What your organization can do

- Identify staff to work with different KP groups and provide them with training
- Assess your resources and capacities to offer quality care to KP groups. Celebrate your strengths and address your weaknesses or gaps
- Be an advocate for compassion

- Know your referral resources for KP groups in your area. If your organization is not well-equipped to serve members of key populations groups, refer.
- Ask the organizations you're referring to what support you could provide them. Ask those organizations to provide a training for your staff.
- Consider working with peer advocate

